

มหาวิทยาลัยมหิดล
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Wisdom of the Land

Machine learning (ML) techniques

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The failure of Digital Government is caused by...

Planning > Understanding
Regulation > Implementation

Quick Comparison

Feature	X-Axis	Y-Axis
Direction	Horizontal (Left-Right)	Vertical (Up-Down)
Alternate Name	Abscissa	Ordinate
Common Variable	Independent (e.g., Time)	Dependent (e.g., Temperature)
Equation	$y = 0$	$x = 0$

Components of an XY Graph

- **The Axes:** The x-axis is a horizontal number line, while the y-axis is a vertical number line.
- **The Origin:** The central point where the two axes meet is called the origin, located at the coordinates **(0, 0)**.

Machine learning (ML) techniques

- ▶ methodologies used to build models that learn patterns from data to make predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed

ML techniques are generally categorized into **five major learning paradigms** based on the type of data and feedback used during training.

Supervised Learning:

The model is trained on "labeled" data, where both input and the correct output are provided.

- ▶ **Classification:** Assigning data into discrete categories (e.g., [filtering spam emails](#)).
- ▶ **Regression:** Predicting continuous numerical values (e.g., [forecasting house prices](#)).

Unsupervised Learning: The model works with "unlabeled" data to find hidden patterns or structures on its own.

- ▶ **Clustering:** Grouping similar data points together (e.g., [customer segmentation](#)).
- ▶ **Dimensionality Reduction:** Simplifying data by reducing the number of variables while keeping the most important information (e.g., [Principal Component Analysis](#)).

Reinforcement Learning (RL)

- ▶ An agent learns to make decisions by interacting with an environment to maximize "rewards" through trial and error (e.g., [training robots or self-driving cars](#)).
- ▶ **Regression:** Predicting continuous numerical values interacting with an environment based on regression data / time series (e.g., forecasting budget).

Semi-Supervised Learning

- ▶ Combines a small amount of labeled data with a large amount of unlabeled data to improve accuracy when labeling is expensive.

Self-Supervised Learning

- ▶ The model generates its own labels from the data itself, often used in large language models (LLMs) and [computer vision](#).

Common ML Algorithms & Techniques

- ▶ **Linear Regression:** Fits a linear relationship between input and output.
- ▶ **Decision Trees & Random Forests:** Tree-like models used for classification and regression.
- ▶ **Support Vector Machines (SVM):** Finds the best boundary (hyperplane) to separate data classes.

Common ML Algorithms & Techniques

- ▶ **Neural Networks & Deep Learning:** Multi-layered architectures inspired by the human brain for complex tasks like image and speech recognition.
- ▶ **Ensemble Methods:** Combining multiple models to improve overall prediction accuracy.
- ▶ **Transfer Learning:** Reusing a pre-trained model for a new but related task to save time and data.

Principal Component Analysis, Machine learning (ML) techniques

1. Sample Dataset

Suppose we have a dataset with 3 samples and 2 features (x, y):

- $A = (2, 3)$
- $B = (3, 4)$
- $C = (4, 5)$

Principal Component Analysis

Step 1: Center the Data

Calculate the mean of each feature and subtract it from each data point.

- **Mean (x):** $(2 + 3 + 4)/3 = 3$
- **Mean (y):** $(3 + 4 + 5)/3 = 4$

Centered Data Matrix ($X_{centered}$):

- A' : $(2 - 3, 3 - 4) = (-1, -1)$
- B' : $(3 - 3, 4 - 4) = (0, 0)$
- C' : $(4 - 3, 5 - 4) = (1, 1)$

Principal Component Analysis

Step 2: Calculate the Covariance Matrix (S)

The covariance matrix S for 2 variables is a 2×2 matrix:

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} \text{Var}(x) & \text{Cov}(x, y) \\ \text{Cov}(y, x) & \text{Var}(y) \end{bmatrix}$$

Using the formula $\text{Cov}(x, y) = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{n - 1}$:

- $\text{Var}(x) = \frac{(-1)^2 + 0^2 + 1^2}{3 - 1} = \frac{2}{2} = 1$
- $\text{Var}(y) = \frac{(-1)^2 + 0^2 + 1^2}{3 - 1} = \frac{2}{2} = 1$
- $\text{Cov}(x, y) = \frac{(-1)(-1) + (0)(0) + (1)(1)}{3 - 1} = \frac{2}{2} = 1$

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Resulting Covariance Matrix:

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Principal Component Analysis

Step 3: Find Eigenvalues (λ)

Solve the characteristic equation $\det(S - \lambda I) = 0$:

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1 - \lambda & 1 \\ 1 & 1 - \lambda \end{vmatrix} = (1 - \lambda)^2 - 1 = 0$$
$$\lambda^2 - 2\lambda = 0 \implies \lambda(\lambda - 2) = 0$$

- $\lambda_1 = 2$ (Largest eigenvalue, becomes **PC1**)
- $\lambda_2 = 0$ (Second largest, becomes **PC2**)

Step 1: Form the matrix $(S - \lambda I)$

The original matrix S is implicitly $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$. The identity matrix I is $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$.

Multiply the identity matrix by λ and subtract it from S :

$$S - \lambda I = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} - \lambda \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \lambda & 1 \\ 1 & 1 - \lambda \end{pmatrix}$$

This matches the matrix inside the determinant bars in your image.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 - \lambda & 1 \\ 1 & 1 - \lambda \end{pmatrix}$$

Step 2: Calculate the determinant and set it to zero

For a 2x2 matrix $\begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$, the determinant is calculated as $(a \cdot d) - (b \cdot c)$. We set this result to zero to form the characteristic equation:

$$\det(S - \lambda I) = (1 - \lambda)(1 - \lambda) - (1 \cdot 1) = 0$$

Expand and Simplify the Equation

Step 1: Expand the binomial $(1 - \lambda)^2$

The expression $(1 - \lambda)^2$ means $(1 - \lambda) \times (1 - \lambda)$. You can use the FOIL (First, Outer, Inner, Last) method or the general formula for a perfect square trinomial, $(a - b)^2 = a^2 - 2ab + b^2$, where $a = 1$ and $b = \lambda$:

$$(1 - \lambda)^2 = 1^2 - 2(1)(\lambda) + \lambda^2$$

$$(1 - \lambda)^2 = 1 - 2\lambda + \lambda^2$$

The original equation becomes:

$$(1 - 2\lambda + \lambda^2) - 1 = 0$$

Step 2: Simplify by combining constant terms

Remove the parenthesis and combine the constant terms (1 and -1):

$$1 - 2\lambda + \lambda^2 - 1 = 0$$

$$(1 - 1) - 2\lambda + \lambda^2 = 0$$

$$0 - 2\lambda + \lambda^2 = 0$$

Step 3: Rearrange terms into standard polynomial form

Rearrange the remaining terms in descending order of power for λ :

$$\lambda^2 - 2\lambda = 0$$

Step 3: Solve the characteristic equation for λ

Expand and simplify the equation:

- $(1 - \lambda)^2 - 1 = 0$

- $(1 - 2\lambda + \lambda^2) - 1 = 0$

- $\lambda^2 - 2\lambda = 0$

Factor the quadratic equation:

- $\lambda(\lambda - 2) = 0$

This equation gives two possible solutions for λ :

- $\lambda_1 = 2$

- $\lambda_2 = 0$

When applying the reverse of the distributive property, $ab + ac$, we compare it directly to the terms in the equation $\lambda^2 - 2\lambda$:

- The first term is λ^2 , which corresponds to ab .
- The second term is -2λ , which corresponds to ac .

The equation $\lambda(\lambda - 2) = 0$ gives two possible solutions due to a fundamental mathematical rule called the **Zero Product Property**.

The Zero Product Property

This property states: If you multiply two or more factors together and the result is zero, then at least one of those individual factors *must* be equal to zero.

In your equation, $\lambda(\lambda - 2) = 0$, we have two factors being multiplied:

1. **Factor 1:** λ
2. **Factor 2:** $(\lambda - 2)$

Principal Component Analysis

Step 4: Find Eigenvectors (v)

For $\lambda_1 = 2$, solve $(S - 2I)v = 0$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \implies -v_1 + v_2 = 0 \implies v_1 = v_2$$

Normalizing the vector so its length is 1 gives: $v_1 = [0.707, 0.707]^T$.

Principal Component Analysis

Step 5: Transform the Data

Multiply the centered data by the eigenvector v_1 to project it into 1D space:

- **New A :** $(-1 \times 0.707) + (-1 \times 0.707) = -1.414$
- **New B :** $(0 \times 0.707) + (0 \times 0.707) = 0$
- **New C :** $(1 \times 0.707) + (1 \times 0.707) = 1.414$

Conclusion: The original 2D data is now reduced to a 1D line where **PC1** captures 100% of the variance (since $\lambda_1/(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) = 2/2 = 1.0$).

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Q&A